

Psychosocial Factors at Work: A Case Study among Salesmen in an Indonesian Automotive Company

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ABSTRACT: Human resources are the most vital for organizations to achieve their goals. In today's world where all the business operations are advancing, and competition is increasing, the performance of an employee is the vital source for survival. Performance is also characterized by the visible actions (i.e., behaviors) of individuals that are pertinent to the organization's objectives. Regarding productivity, a systematic review found that psychosocial plays a role in explaining the quality and quantity aspects of shaping company productivity. The psychosocial condition of an employee is a form of reaction that the employee gives psychologically to his work and work environment, including his social relationships in the workplace such as with leaders, coworkers, or customers.

An Indonesian automotive company's growth productivity is based on the unit sales by the salesman, market share, and Key Performance Indicator (KPI). Somehow, there is a decrease in their productivity. To address these circumstances, this study intends to explore psychosocial conditions that affect performance. This research intends to apply COPSOQ III to salesmen as a screening to the company, and to gain an understanding of which psychosocial factors that may impact on performance of the salesmen (N = 334). COPSOQ III consists of 147 items, 45 factors and grouped into eight domains.

Data were analysed using Pearson product-moment correlation with significance level (p value <0.05) are conducted to analyse COPSOQ III as measurement. Result shows that, mostly salesmen have issues in their health-well-being, demands at work, work organization and job contents, interpersonal relations and leadership, and work individual interface. The findings also explore significant correlation between burnout and some dimensions in health-well-being. Quality of leadership also strongly correlated with predictability, role clarity, social support from supervisors, organizational justice, and recognition.

KEYWORDS: Organization Resources, Psychosocial at Work, Salesman Productivity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Organizations are set on attaining specific objectives. To do so, they require essential human, financial, and physical assets. While the extent of these resources varies across organizations, it is generally recognized that human resources are the most vital for organizations to achieve their goals (Tessema, Tesfom, Faircloth, Tesfagiorgis and Teckle, 2022). In today's world where all the business operations are advancing, and competition is increasing, the performance of an employee is the vital source for survival (Mughal, 2020). It is crucial for the success of an organization that employees be highly involved in their jobs (Kaur and Randhawa, 2021). Companies will require their employees to exceed expectations in various manners, not merely through increased effort, but by demonstrating resilience, a capacity for learning, adaptability, and speed (Aon Hewitt, 2014; Popli and Rizvi, 2016).

The ability to adapt to rapid change has become a key success criterion for both individuals and organizations (Ulrich and Yeung, 2019). To attain competitive advantage, organizations are more concerned with the skills and the quality of their employees to ensure sustained performance (Akhtar, Aamir, Khurshid, Abro and Hussain, 2015). The job performance is defined as the aggregated financial or non-financial benefit by the employees in contribution to the fulfillment both indirectly and directly to the targeted organizational goals (Mughal, 2020). Performance is also characterized by the visible actions (i.e., behaviors) of individuals that are pertinent to the organization's objectives (Campbell, McHenry and Wise, 1990).

Performance is not just important for organizational outcomes but also for an individual's self-concept and self-esteem (Bandura, 1977; Rodríguez-Cifuentes, Segura-Camacho, García-Ael, and Topa, 2020). Performance is also defined as measurable actions, behaviors, and results that employees participate in or produce, which are associated with and aid in achieving organizational objectives (Viswesvaran and Ones, 2000; Koopmans, Bernaards, Hildebrandt, Schaufeli, De Vet and Van Der Beek, 2011). People

vary in their performance under identical conditions and due to different reasons. Hence, understanding the underlying factors of performance is crucial to foster it effectively (Bal and De Lange, 2014; Rodríguez-Cifuentes et al., 2020).

Health, encompassing both physical and mental well-being, is a key factor in addressing new challenges associated with workplace productivity, performance, and job satisfaction (Ginting and Febriansyah, 2020). Health conditions in the workplace serve as a reflection of the quality of life for employees, encompassing physical, social, and psychological dimensions (Kuoppala, Lamminpaa, and Husman, 2008; Ginting and Febriansyah, 2020). Prioritizing employee health is crucial for companies, as it not only fosters high productivity but also helps in minimizing medical costs. (Jonathan and Mbogo, 2016; Ginting and Febriansyah, 2020).

Regarding productivity, a systematic review found that psychosocial plays a role in explaining the quality and quantity aspects of it (Aboagye et al., 2021; Toivanen, Berthelsen and Muhonen, 2023). Supported by Siegrist and Marmot (2004; Egan et al., 2008) described the psychosocial as the spectrum of socio structural possibilities accessible to an individual for fulfilling their needs for well-being, productivity, and positive self-experience. The psychosocial condition of an employee is a form of reaction that the employee gives psychologically to his work and work environment, including his social relationships in the workplace such as with leaders, coworkers, or customers (Shimazu, Nordin, Dollard and Oakman, 2016).

In Indonesia, psychosocial problems are also starting to emerge and receive attention. The Ministry of Health regulates employee occupational health through Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 11 of 2022 concerning the Implementation of Occupational Disease Services (Pelayanan Kesehatan Penyakit Akibat Kerja). One of the causes of occupational disease that is highlighted in the regulation is the psychosocial group which includes qualitative and quantitative workload, work organization, monotonous work, interpersonal relations, shift work, and work location (Permenkes No. 11 tahun 2022, n.d.).

Understanding the health conditions of employees enables companies to tailor activities that promote physical fitness, psychological well-being, and social health in the workplace. This approach contributes to fostering a positive organizational atmosphere (Ginting and Febriansyah, 2020). Knowing the importance of employee health, psychosocial factors, and overall well-being is vital for a healthy work environment and productivity. Indeed, it is important to be attentive to such aspects.

The study is set in the context of a leading automotive dealership company in Indonesia. The research aims to analyze the psychosocial conditions of salesmen in the company, and the key psychosocial conditions experienced by salesmen that impact performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Psychosocial

Psychosocial means a broad term that encompasses both the psychological and social facets of an individual (Oxford English Dictionary, 2023). A psychosocial perspective on human behavior examines the interplay between internal psychological factors and external environmental elements that involves emotional, social and physical components (Vizzotto et al., 2013; Eiroá-Orosa, 2020).

Psychosocial epidemiology investigates how individuals' interactions with their social surroundings can impact health, either directly (such as biological reactions to what is often termed as 'stress') or indirectly through health-related behaviors (Egan, Tannahill, Petticrew and Thomas, 2008). Psychosocial traits are also often defined as a person's psychological growth in the context of their social and cultural surroundings (Vizzotto et al., 2013).

Psychosocial health is a dynamic state encompassing the mutual adaptation and interdependence between a person and their social surroundings. This social environment includes relationships and networks like family, friends, or colleagues, along with the social frameworks present in that environment. Psychosocial health represents a fluctuating condition, varying across different life stages or events. It can be strengthened through the activation of resources or support, such as emotional support or personal relational skills, or it can be undermined by exposure to risks like work-related stress, traumatic incidents, or illness (Peter, Helfer, Halfens and Hahn, 2021).

B. Psychosocial at Work

The term 'psychosocial work environment' has been utilized since at least 1982, with various attempts to define it. The underlying purpose is to concentrate on the work environment, pinpointing factors within the employer's control to enhance job satisfaction and overall well-being (Rugulies, 2018; Breedt, Marais and Patricios, 2023). Psychosocial work conditions refer to interpersonal and social dynamics within the workplace that impact behavior and professional growth (Breedt et al., 2023).

Psychosocial factors in the workplace play a crucial role in shaping company productivity. Improved psychosocial conditions correlate with enhanced productivity, while challenges in these areas can negatively impact overall company performance and employee satisfaction. These facts underscore the significance of addressing psychosocial conditions in the work environment to maintain and improve both productivity and employee contentment (Ginting and Febriansyah, 2020).

Psychosocial concepts in the workplace describe relationships between employees (human-to-human) and employee interactions with the work situations they face. Psychosocial factors in the workplace describe the complex interactions between employees and work-related factors. Therefore, psychosocial factors in the workplace can be analyzed based on the type of work, work processing and planning, the qualifications needed by employees to do the work, and how employees face and respond to work situations. Psychosocial factors in the workplace consist of two large groups. The first group is factors related to the employee's self or individual, both physical and mental. The second group is factors related to the work environment, both physical and social (Ginting and Febriansyah, 2020).

Apart from psychosocial factors, to understand the psychosocial environmental conditions in the workplace, it is also necessary to understand the psychosocial risks in the workplace that may occur. Psychosocial hazards and risk factors in the workplace pertain to elements within work organizations that are created by human design, carrying the potential for psychological or physical harm. These factors often involve human relations and encompass aspects like the organization and management of work, social and relational components of work, and job design (Cox and Griffiths, 2005; Oakman, Dollard, Shimazu and Nordin, 2016). Recognized psychosocial risk factors at work, such as poor organizational climate, work pressure, job insecurity, bullying, violence, and general work-related stress, are increasingly acknowledged as threats to both workers' psychological and physical well-being, as well as to organizational performance and productivity (Commission on Social Determinants of Health, 2008; Oakman et al., 2016).

C. The Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire (COPSOQ III)

There are various measurement models of psychosocial factors in the workplace used in the world. One of the most complete, progressive, and with a strong theoretical foundation is the Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire or what is often called COPSOQ (Ginting and Febriansyah, 2020). COPSOQ is a measurement tool designed for workplace assessments, typically used to compare work groups, departments, or entire companies, as well as for research purposes, such as examining the impact of the work environment on health or labor market success (Berthelsen, Westerlund, Bergström and Burr, 2020).

Basically, COPSOQ can be used for two purposes, as to conducting occupational risk and health assessments in the workplace. From 1995 to 2007, the Danish National Research Center research group led by Tage S. Kristensen and Vilhelm Borg developed COPSOQ which is still being developed by the International COPSOQ Network. Currently, COPSOQ has become a measurement model that is widely used to measure psychosocial risk and has been cited in several important documents published by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the International Labor Organization (ILO). Apart from that, COPSOQ also received the title of best practice from the European Union's Occupational Health and Safety Agency based on the results of measurements that have been carried out on an international scale (Ginting and Febriansyah, 2020).

COPSOQ was designed to measure psychosocial risks and conditions in the workplace. This questionnaire can be used for all types of work from various organizations and industries. The results of these measurements are not intended to judge the company, but on the contrary to identify and make improvements to factors that hinder the company's growth. The main domain and psychosocial factors measured are generic so they can be applied to various types and sizes of corporate organizations.

The COPSOQ instrument has been translated into 25 languages and has been used in more than 40 countries in the world. Nowadays, COPSOQ has been developed from COPSOQ I and II, into COPSOQ III. Initially, the first version of COPSOQ consisted of 30 factors grouped into seven domains. In 2007, the second version of COPSOQ was published adding 11 factors so that the total factors measured in COPSOQ II were 41 factors. Currently, COPSOQ III, which consists of 45 factors and grouped into eight domains (Ginting and Febriansyah, 2020).

The COPSOQ III questionnaire is the latest version, incorporating insights from previous studies, particularly COPSOQ I and II, to comprehensively address psychosocial factors in the workplace. COPSOQ III consists of a number of factors that can cover broad domains. The international COPSOQ network acknowledges that not all organizations or industries require an analysis of all psychosocial factors in COPSOQ III. Hence, COPSOQ III is segmented into three versions—short, middle, and long—providing a progressively comprehensive and precise measurement tool for characterizing psychosocial conditions in the workplace.

COPSOQ III Indonesian version has tested before to which 4,091 employees (managers to staff) from state-owned and private organizations have completed the 147 questionnaire items contained in the Indonesian version of COPSOQ III. All questionnaire items represent 45 psychosocial factors in the long version of COPSOQ III. The results of the analysis that have been carried out show that all COPSOQ III Indonesian versions have met the validity and reliability tests to measure the expected psychosocial factors and are grouped into the same domains as in the international version of COPSOQ III (Ginting and Febriansyah, 2020).

Measurements using COPSOQ III offer numerous advantages, benefiting not only companies and the government but also various functions within the organizational structure. This tool provides valuable information for identifying priority preventive actions against specific psychosocial risk factors. The overarching objective is to establish healthy and safe working conditions for employees, irrespective of their roles, positions, or social circumstances. Ensuring employees can work in a healthy and secure environment, both physically and mentally, can significantly enhance the company's productivity and profits (Ginting and Febriansyah, 2020).

Table II.1 Domain and Dimensions in COPSOQ III

Domain	Dimension	Label
Health and Well-Being	Self-rated Health	GH
	Cognitive Stress	CS
	Somatic Stress	SO
	Sleeping Troubles	SL
	Stress	ST
	Burnout	BO
	Depressive Symptoms	DS
Demands at Work	Cognitive Demands	CD
	Emotional Demands	ED
	Work Pace	WP
	Demands for Hiding Emotions	HE
	Quantitative Demands	QD
Work Organization and Job Contents	Possibilities for Development	PD
	Meaning of Work	MW
	Influence at Work	IN
	Variation of Work	VA
	Control Over Working Time	CT
Interpersonal Relations and Leadership	Recognition	RE
	Quality of Leadership	QL
	Predictability	PR
	Role Clarity	CL
	Social Support from Supervisors	SS
	Sense of Community at Work	SW
	Social Support from Colleagues	SC
	Illegitimate Task	IT
	Role Conflicts	CO

Domain	Dimension	Label
Work-Individual Interface	Job Satisfaction	JS
	Quality of Work	QW
	Work Engagement	WE
	Commitment to the Workplace	CW
	Work Life Conflict	WF
	Insecurity Over Working Conditions	IW
	Job Insecurity	JU
Social Capital	Horizontal Trust	TM
	Vertical Trust	RE
	Organizational Justice	JI
Conflict and Offensive Behavior	Unpleasant Teasing	UT
	Threats of Violence	TV
	Sexual Harrasment	SH
	Physical Violence	PV
	Harassment in Social Media	HSM
	Gossip and Slander	GS
	Conflict and Quarrels	CQ
	Bullying	BU
Personality	Self-Efficacy	SE

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this research, a quantitative method was used with a questionnaire as one of the primary sources of data. Questionnaires in this research use COPSOQ III which consists of 8 domains, 45 dimensions, and 147 items with 10 different response alternatives. COPSOQ was initially designed for workplace risk assessment (Burr et al., 2019). It offers short, middle, and long versions, customizable based on the purpose, whether it be risk assessment or research. Each version includes specific required items from various domains to ensure standardized usage. COPSOQ III questionnaire is the latest version, considering psychosocial factors in the workplace that have been developed in previous studies, especially from COPSOQ I and II. The development of the third version was prompted by emerging trends in work life, incorporating theoretical concepts such as the job demands-resources (JD-R) model (Breedt et al., 2023).

In this study, the researcher applied the Slovin formula to identify the sample size from the population of employees. From a total of 466 salespeople, the Slovin formula was utilized to accurately calculate the number of samples needed from the overall population.

$$n = \frac{466}{1 + 466 (0,05)^2}$$

As a result, the study involved a minimum sample of 216 employees who were expected to take part in the survey, determined through the application of Slovin's formula.

IV. FINDINGS

As part of the COPSOQ III questionnaire, the respondents are required to fill in the demographic information. In this study, researchers utilize Erikson's psychosocial developmental stages model, as outlined by Chung (2018), to classify participants into four distinct age groups.

Figure IV.1 Demographic of Respondents' Age

- Early young adulthood (18-25 years): For only 5,1% are in this age group.
- Late young adulthood (25-40 years): This age group dominated the distribution of respondents by 76,9%.
- Early middle adulthood (40-50 years): This age group secondly dominated the distribution of respondents by 16,5%.
- Late middle adulthood (Above 50 years): Only 5 people (1,5%) accounted for this age group.

Figure IV.2 Demographic of Respondents' Gender

The gender distribution of those who participated in the questionnaire consists of 81% male employees, while the remaining 19% comprises female employees. The majority of respondents' educational background is bachelor's degree (57%), followed by high school degree (31%) and Diploma III (11%). The majority of respondents in this study had been serving in the current company for over four years (48%), with the next largest groups comprising individuals with less than two years (31%) and those with an occupancy between two and four years (21%).

A. Domain I: Health & Well-Being

The study showed that salesmen have good self-rated health (78%). Meanwhile, some dimensions require additional consideration because they have an average score below 50. It is cognitive stress (29%) and burnout (27%).

Cognitive stress, as defined in COPSOQ III by Ginting and Febriansyah (2020), refers to cognitive indicators of ongoing stress reactions and is quantifiable. When employees need to use additional effort in comprehending their work duties and obligations can lead to negative cognitive stress. This heightened cognitive load may result in a decline in physical health, manifested through complaints such as stomach ache or pain in various body parts, along with other somatic stress symptoms. Conversely, employees

not affected by cognitive stress tend to experience better overall health conditions (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Kristensen et al., 2005). Moreover, cognitive stress exhibits a significant positive correlation with factors like workload, interpersonal conflict, and organizational demands. Employees grappling with cognitive stress may face reduced productivity due to impaired cognitive functions, including compromised thinking and memory abilities (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Dicke et al., 2018).

Furthermore, psychological fatigue or boredom, commonly known as burnout, is frequently understood as a response to various work demands. Individuals experiencing burnout experience continuing emotional exhaustion, as outlined in COPSOQ III, characterized by continuous physical and mental fatigue (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Burr et al., 44 2019). This prolonged exhaustion leads to diminished concentration levels at work and a tendency for employees to neglect their responsibilities (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Kristensen et al., 2005). The factor of fatigue or burnout is also thought to deplete an employee's energy, resulting in physical tiredness. Employees in this state often encounter challenges in performing the necessary tasks to fulfill their job responsibilities. Typically, they quickly feel physically tired and exhibit a lack of enthusiasm for their work, ultimately contributing to a decline in work productivity (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Burr et al., 2019).

B. Domain II: Demands at Work

In this domain we need to consider two dimensions. There are cognitive demands (64%) and work pace (60%). Ginting and Febriansyah (2020) stated that concerning the psychosocial aspects of the workplace, it is essential to take into account the management of cognitive demands at both individual and organizational levels to uphold a balanced work environment. Insufficient cognitive demands in a job are a risk to diminishing the competitive advantage of a company. Conversely, excessively high cognitive demands in the workplace can lead to heightened stress among employees, resulting in periodic declines in work productivity. The association between high cognitive demands, reflected in a significant workload and elevated expectations from the company, is considered standard for enhancing efficiency in various work sectors and responding to competency requirements. However, if these demands are not adequately managed, they can evolve into a mental burden to employees. This situation may be further compounded by job characteristics that become increasingly unpredictable. In such conditions, employees with lower abilities and readiness are prone to psychosocial risks, with stress and depression being potential side effects (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020). To mitigate these risks, it is crucial for the cognitive demands of a job to align with the employee's capabilities and preparedness. Companies can take steps to enhance employees' cognitive abilities and readiness for job demands by providing relevant training. Additionally, a consistent evaluation process is essential to gauge employee perceptions regarding the level of cognitive demands associated with their work (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020).

Meanwhile, work pace stands as a critical factor for companies to effectively respond to competitive demands, where rapid actions are essential across all aspects of business. Increasing work pace is viewed as a means to enhance productivity at a consistent cost. Although this approach is often adopted by companies striving to achieve their goals, prolonged implementation may disrupt the psychosocial well-being of employees, ultimately diminishing overall company productivity (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020). Faced with the pressure of heightened productivity expectations, employees often perceive that the workload exceeds the available time. This requires employees to optimize their time by accelerating the work pace to meet deadlines. Success in coping with the demand for increased work speed is often associated with employees possessing strong cognitive and psychomotor skills, while those failure to meet speed demands can lead to the emergence of psychosocial risks, prompting negative responses from employees towards their work environment, which can have detrimental effects on both the company and the individuals (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020).

C. Domain III: Work Organization and Job Contents

Within these dimensions, the meaning of work dimension has the highest average score (83%). Moreover, two dimensions have an average score below 50; variation of work (49%) and control over working time (45%).

Control over working time is an increasingly crucial role for workers to integrate, balance or harmonize their work and non-work lives. Employees lacking control over their work hours often find themselves spending excessive time at work and often feel like they are running out of time to enjoy things outside of work. This situation will encourage the creation of conflict between work life and personal life. Apart from that, employees' low ability to control working time also has the potential to cause failure in completing their work. Control over working time is not only determined by internal factors such as an individual's ability and level of authority, but can also be influenced by external factors such as company policies and regulations. The International Labor Organization (ILO) has set a total of 48 hours per week. It is essential for companies to ensure fair distribution of work within the

workplace, and will give employees the right to appropriate working time, whether for working hours, rest time, or holiday time (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020).

D. Domain IV: Interpersonal Relations and Leadership

Seven out of nine dimensions in the domain show an average score above 50, except illegitimate task dimension (41%) and role conflicts dimension (43%). The highest average score is in role clarity dimension (82%), followed by sense of community dimension (80%) and social support from supervisor dimension (77%).

Illegitimate task or non-formal task focuses on the conflict between the extrinsic qualities of a task and the role expected of a person in the workplace. The high intensity of unimportant assignments in the workplace makes it a form of stressor in the workplace. Task-related stressors can threaten employees in several ways. Demands that are too high, unclear, or conflicting can cause mental stress for employees. As a result, employees have the potential to lose work concentration which results in poor performance outcomes. Failure to achieve performance standards can threaten employees, both in terms of self-evaluation as a competent individual (related to employee appreciation for themselves) and in evaluations carried out by the organization (related to social rewards in the workplace). In other words, employees who feel they have failed in achieving work standards will feel less competent, which will lead to a loss of employee confidence in their work. Although non-formal tasks are not always difficult for employees to complete, they violate employee role identity norms based on the requirements to carry out work demands (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020).

When individuals engage with their social environment, including interactions within organizational settings, they inevitably encounter the risk of incongruity and conflicts, with role conflict in the workplace being a notable example. Employees undergoing role conflict often experience heightened job pressure, and if sustained, this can lead to adverse mental health outcomes such as stress and depression. Furthermore, the inability to fulfill assigned roles generates a sense of disappointment and diminishes employees' confidence in their ability to accomplish tasks, resulting in lower job satisfaction (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020). The inadequate quality of leadership and support provided to subordinates may indicate a supervisor's incapacity to organize task schedules or delineate roles for each employee, leading to role overlap and, consequently, role conflict. Consequently, employees may lose trust in their superiors and experience dissatisfaction with their work (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020). A higher frequency of assigning non-formal tasks to employees correlates with increased role conflict in the workplace, along with a lack of clarity regarding employee roles and recognition of their achievements at work. This situation diminishes the predictability of work, as employees burdened with non-formal tasks find themselves dedicating substantial time to duties beyond their official obligations (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Burr et al., 2019).

E. Domain V: Work Individual Interface

All dimensions in this domain have an average score above 50, and work engagement dimension has the highest average score (82%). There are two dimensions with average scores below 50 in the survey results. Specifically, the insecurity over working conditions (36%) and the work-life conflict (29%).

Employees who exhibit high involvement and commitment to their work can position themselves positively within the company, responding favorably to any changes and alleviating concerns about their current working conditions. Meanwhile, levels of anxiety and insecurity persist among various groups of employees, especially those with contract status (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Silla, Gracia & Peiro, 2005). Considering that the company has partner salespeople who are also considered contracted employees, it can be explained that the average score in this dimension is also high. The concern regarding working conditions is linked to both the physical and psychological security aspects of work, particularly concerning work content. Worries about working conditions stem from the potential for changes in working hours, alterations in salary components that may decrease the nominal salary, and the typical human resource allocation characterized by employee movements from one location to another (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Burr et al., 2019).

Work-life conflict arises when the demands and obligations at the workplace do not align with the requirements of roles beyond work. This conflict can manifest in both directions, with work demands interrupt on personal and family responsibilities, or personal and family demands affect work (Ginting and Febriansyah, 2020). Prolonged conflicts between work and life can adversely affect employee health, making it challenging for them to maintain focus at work. Consequently, employees may experience

diminished capacity to perform work activities effectively, leading to a decline in the overall quality of work (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Burr et al., 2019).

F. Domain VI: Social Capital

All dimensions have an average score above 50, with the highest average score is organizational justice dimension (71%) and the lowest average score is in horizontal trust dimension (65%).

Trust between employees plays an important role in business continuity not only in the short term but also in the long term. Without trust between employees, the company will have difficulty in continuing the work relay. If there was no trust between employees, coordination and exchange of information would be impossible. Each employee will tend to ignore each other, so there is no interaction between employees. Obstruction of the information process and cooperation between employees will not only hinder existing business processes but also hinder the development of the skills and abilities of each individual within it, resulting in less optimal work productivity. Low levels of trust between employees can also create a poor psychosocial environment in the workplace. Without mutual trust, employees will tend to have high concerns about the whereabouts of their co-workers. This has the potential to encourage employees to tend to feel jealous, anxious and wary of the achievements of their colleagues. Not infrequently, low trust between employees can create feelings of suspicion among employees (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020). On the other hand, employees who share mutual trust will effectively coordinate their work, readily collaborate, and exchange information. Consequently, productivity levels will rise as employees collaborate to achieve the company's established goals. This collaborative atmosphere fosters a positive workplace environment, contributing to the development of an improved psychosocial setting. Trust among employees is also nurtured when the company treats each employee fairly. In this case, every employee with the same position level will feel that they have the same status, rights and obligations so that employees 50 together will build psychosocial conditions in the workplace that tend to be positive (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020).

G. Domain VIII: Personality

The personality dimension that explains self-efficacy has an average score exceeding 50, contributing 75%.

H. Domain VII: Conflicts and Offensive Behavior

This study found that unpleasant teasing dimension mostly happened at all frequencies, ranging from a few times (132 respondents), monthly (19 respondents), weekly (12 respondents), until daily (9 respondents).

Within COPSOQ III, unpleasant teasing is a measured factor because it is believed to impact employees' comfort levels at work. Consequently, when unpleasant teasing happens in the workplace employees may restrict their interactions within the social environment at work, ultimately leading to a decline in work quality and productivity (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Burr et al., 2019).

Further, gossip and slander reported daily to the respondents (5 respondents). Gossip is a prevalent form of informal communication in the workplace that often leads to negative consequences. A work environment characterized by gossip and slander faces challenges such as diminished trust, respect, and concern among employees. Ultimately, gossip and slander in the workplace can exert a detrimental influence on employee attitudes and behavior (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Rossouw & Van Vuuren, 2004). Individuals surrounded by gossip and slander may struggle to trust others and encounter difficulties in cultivating positive working relationships with colleagues. Employees who become targets of gossip and slander often experience heightened anxiety and may even suffer from depression if they are unable to deny the rumors. 51 According to self-verification theory (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Swann, 2012), gossip and slander in the workplace can impact the employee's self-evaluation process in three ways. First, victims of gossip and slander may tend to evaluate themselves negatively, making it challenging for them to develop their abilities and focusing on negative aspects related to their work. Consequently, employees may lose confidence in their work abilities. Second, when victims perceive gossip and slander as unwanted interpersonal interactions, it can lead to significant psychological burdens. Gossip and slander often cause excessive worry and alertness, contributing to stress and depression (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Probst et al., 2007). The third impact is that a work environment filled with gossip and slander erodes mutual trust among employees, fostering mutual suspicion, hostility, and noncooperation. In such circumstances, employees are susceptible to negative emotions like anxiety, anger, and depression. Moreover, employees in the same work environment, even if not directly exposed to gossip, may develop similar mental health problems due to the fear of becoming the next victim of gossip and slander. Such employees may experience elevated anxiety levels in the workplace (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020; Kong, 2018).

Generally, in all dimensions reported that managers/ supervisor and colleagues dominate encounter conflict and offensive behavior. For further detail will explain below.

1. For 20% respondents appeared to have had unpleasant teasing carried by managers/ supervisor, followed by colleagues for 16% and client for 3%.
2. Threats of violence reported that 4% were accused by managers/ supervisors, then each of 2% followed by clients, colleagues, and subordinates.
3. For 1,8% respondents reported that they experienced sexual harassment by clients, followed by 1,5% carried by managers/ supervisors. colleagues, and subordinates.
4. Moreover, 2,4% respondents noted that managers/ supervisors were accused of physical violence, followed by subordinates and colleagues for 1,5%.
5. Cyber bullying is mostly accused by clients (9,3%), then managers/ supervisors (2,1%) and colleagues (1,2%).
6. Gossip and slander are the second most reported experiences by respondents. 12,6% reported their colleagues as the source for this behavior, followed by managers/ supervisors (2,4%) and subordinates (1,8%).
7. For the bullying dimension, respondents reported that they were mostly accused by colleagues (4,5%), managers/ supervisors (3%), and subordinates (1,2%).
8. Bullying that turned into unfairly criticized behavior, the primary sources of accusations were mainly colleagues (13,2%), followed by managers/supervisors (6,6%), and subordinates (2,4%).

H. Correlation between COPSOQ III Domain

Correlation analysis using Pearson correlation to explore the linear relationship between domains. The correlations indicate the strength and significance of the relationships between different dimensions. Some dimensions that show positive significant correlations with strong or very strong correlation are:

1. **Burnout is strongly correlated with sleeping troubles ($r=0.615$), stress ($r=0.706$), somatic stress ($r=0.676$) and depressive symptoms ($r=0.745$).**

Psychosocial stressors in the workplace are often associated with increased depressive symptoms. Basically, this can be prevented by creating good social relationships between employees, supervisors and colleagues (Theorell et al., 2015; Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020). Based on a number of meta-analysis studies conducted by experts, it shows that social support in the workplace, both from supervisors (bosses) and coworkers, can minimize psychosocial risks in the workplace. Psychosocial stressors in the workplace are often associated with increased depressive symptoms. Basically, this can be prevented by creating good social relationships between employees, supervisors and colleagues (Theorell et al. 2015; Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020). Social support from supervisors or superiors requires providing assistance to subordinates regarding their work (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020). There are three forms of social support from supervisors in the workplace which include: 1) Emotional support which shows empathy, acceptance and attention. 2) Informative support, namely providing feedback or guidance in work. 3) Tangible support, namely preparing budgets, resources and real assistance related to work aimed at increasing motivation, performance and effectiveness of subordinates (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020).

2. **Quality of leadership is strongly correlated with predictability ($r=0.701$), role clarity ($r=0.719$), social support from supervisors ($r=0.638$), and organizational justice ($r=0.619$)**

Leadership can be defined as the art of influencing individuals or groups of people so that they are willing to make voluntary efforts to achieve a common goal (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020). Leadership also includes the act of motivating other people to carry out certain tasks. Effective and efficient leaders ensure that the organization's resources are used properly to achieve organizational goals. Therefore, leadership quality is believed to be able to influence an organization's success in facing changes in the business climate, especially in terms of accelerating the flow of information and technological changes (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020). Quality leadership is very important to achieve the vision and mission that have been set, especially in order to face changes that occur both in the internal and external environment (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020). In this research, the result shows that quality of leadership has a positive significant relationship with predictability, role clarity, social support from supervisors, organizational justice, and recognition. Other studies measuring psychosocial conditions in the workplace using COPSOQ also report that the leadership quality factor has a significant positive correlation with predictability, role clarity, and support from superiors (Burr et al., 2019; Kristensen et al., 2005; Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020). Their results explain that leadership quality can be reflected in the leader's ability to

distribute information related to work plans, changes to plan materials, and other important decisions related to work to subordinates. Leadership quality is also closely related to the clarity of the role of each member in the organization on assignment. Delimiting each role in the workplace is necessary to clarify the boundaries of each member's responsibilities so that they can focus on targeted achievements. Apart from that, support from superiors also characterizes good leadership qualities. Overall, these results explain that the higher the level of predictability, role clarity, and support from superiors in the workplace reflects the high quality of leadership in the organization.

3. *Role clarity is strongly correlated with social support from supervisors ($r=0.632$), sense of community at work ($r=0.681$), commitment to the workplace ($r=0.614$), and organizational justice ($r=0.602$).*

Role clarity in this case emphasizes the importance of communication between group members, and it is possible that improving the quality of communication between group members will influence member effectiveness. In other words, a higher level of role clarity in an organization reflects open behavior between employees that originates from understanding and interactive communication about roles within the group (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020). A high level of role clarity will provide many benefits for the organization. It is believed that high role clarity in the organization can improve employee communication, flexibility and responsiveness. High role clarity in the organization can also reduce the risk of stress in employees. In other words, the level of role clarity in the organization can influence the psychosocial conditions of both individuals, groups and organizations (Ginting & Febriansyah, 2020).

These findings illustrate the notable connections between different dimensions of psychology and the work environment, subsequently influencing individuals and their performance.

5. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

This study explains the psychosocial factors of salesmen that are measured using COPSOQ III questionnaire. Findings showed that from eight domain in the COPSOQ III measurement, only two domains that all the dimensions have scored above average (above 50). Social capital and personality domain interpreted as the domain that explain the psychosocial factors at work that remain secure. Meanwhile, another six domains need to be acknowledged, as some dimensions have the average score below 50, considered the domains affected the salesmen performance.

It starts from the health and well-being dimensions, the salesman has cognitive stress, burnout, somatic stress conditions. From demands at work point of view, salesman have cognitive demands and work pace issue. When look at work organization and job contents, the issues are in variation of work and control over working time. They also have some issues in illegitimate task and role conflict when considering interpersonal relations and leadership dimension. From the conflict and offensive behavior domain, it is reported that unpleasant teasing behavior dominated encountered by the salesman ranging from just a few times into daily frequency. Following closely were incidents of gossip and slander, predominantly happening daily. Bullying was reported on a weekly basis, and on a monthly frequency, salesmen also faced threats of violence and incidents of sexual harassment. Last, when reviewing the work-individual interface, salesmen is in insecurity over working conditions and has work-life conflict.

Furthermore, based on the correlation analysis using Pearson Product-Moment correlation explains the key of the psychosocial factors experienced by the salesman that affected their performance. From the correlation analysis showed that from the 45 dimensions have strong positive correlation between another. Dimensions that show significant correlations with strong or very strong correlation are burnout that strongly correlated with sleeping troubles, stress, somatic stress, and depressive symptoms. Second, quality of leadership strongly correlated with predictability, role clarity, social support from supervisors, organizational justice, and recognition. Third, possibilities for development strongly correlated with meaning of work, predictability, and role clarity. Fourth, job satisfaction that very strongly correlated with quality of work. Fifth, organizational justice dimensions strongly correlated with role clarity, predictability, vertical trust, and recognition. Six, role clarity strongly correlated with social support from supervisors, sense of community at work, commitment to the workplace, and organizational justice. Seven, the illegitimate task strongly correlated with role conflicts. These findings illustrate the notable connections between different dimensions of psychological and the work environment, subsequently influencing individual and their performance.

Organizations are advised to adopt programs that apply a holistic approach to workplace development, addressing collaboration, stress coping, cognitive skills, communication, social support, and recognition within the organizational framework. For the managerial implications, considering the reported occurrences of offensive behavior, a more detailed investigation into the

nature and sources of such behavior could be valuable. Some policies also need to be reviewed, regarding limitation hours policy and professional etiquette and communication policy.

Suggestions for further study, may elaborate more on the in-depth analysis of conflict and offensive behavior to explore strategies to address and prevent offensive behavior in the workplace. Comparative studies across different industries or companies could shed light on variations in psychosocial factors and their impact on performance, also by analyzing how organizational cultures differ in addressing these factors and their outcomes could offer valuable insights for improving work environments across diverse contexts. The findings also highlight the correlation between quality of leadership and various dimensions. Future research could delve deeper into the specific leadership styles that contribute positively to employee well-being and performance, providing actionable insights for organizational leadership development.

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